

Progress in artificial components for multisource energy harvesting with living plant leaves

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Abstract—To which extent devices or machines could be constructed by biodegradable or even living components is a crucial question for the sustainable transition of technology. We showed that living plants (instead of dead, plant-derived materials) provide structures and materials that can be used in high-tech devices such as energy harvesters and sensors. Here, we summarize our recent results on exploiting living plants and their materials in plant-hybrid energy harvesters, in which the plant is used to convert a mechanical energy such as from leaves fluttering in the wind and rain drops, and, acting as antenna, to convert radio frequency radiation into electricity. This is realized by modifying the plant with soft artificial materials that do not harm the tissue.

Keywords—Energy, sustainability, bio-inspired robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Plants are inspiration for technical innovation and provide sustainable materials like wood and cellulose extremely useful for multiple applications. Also living plants can directly be exploited in devices, making specifically use of features occurring while alive like ion-conduction, self-healing, and biochemical processes that do not occur artificial materials. Plants perform tasks like producing O_2 and storing CO_2 which are features that cannot easily be obtained in artificial systems.

It was shown that living plants can be used as sensors and energy harvesters exploiting their naturally occurring materials and structures to perform high-tech tasks[1–6]. We are exploring since several years how to adapt artificial components to plants in order to create potential differences from events like leaf fluttering in the wind that are high enough to produce sufficient electricity to power small commercial electronics by converting the mechanical energy into an electricity using the plant tissue as energy converter. Here, we give a chronological overview of the progress of this research in the last years and a snapshot of the results obtained.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Mechanical energy conversion on the leaf surface

In our first study, we reported on the mechanism of contact or tribo-electrification on the leaf surface (a classic example for this mechanism is the static charging of hair when rubbed with a balloon) [1]. We investigated in detail how charges are created on the cuticle, a thin polymer layer and electrical insulator on the outer leaf surface. Interestingly, the inner tissue, containing water and ions is acting as an electrode into which these charges are electrostatically induced, creating a current in the tissue (as illustrated in Fig. 1a). Our study showed that this current is depending on the material which is touching the leaf, the contact area, the force, the frequency of contact, and the plant species [1]. Yet, all tested plant species were able to convert this mechanical stimulus into a current due to the generally similar structure by the tissue acting as electrode and wrapped in the dielectric cuticle. Voltages recorded from a single leaf with an electrode inserted in the

stem were as high as 150 V and could directly power 100 light emitting diodes (LEDs) each time a silicone elastomer touched the leaf (Fig 2b). In fact, our analysis showed that soft, transparent silicones are ideal to obtain high charges while their softness helps not harming the leaf during gentle impacts.

Fig. 1. A) Overview of the mechanism of mechanical energy conversion on a plant leaf based on contact electrification and electrostatic induction. B) Circuit diagram and photograph of 100 LEDs powered by a single plant leaf. Adapted from [1] with permission from Elsevier, © 2018.

B. Producing electricity from wind by fluttering leaves

The system is especially interesting for converting wind energy into electricity. We aimed for devices which can use the fluttering of leaves in the wind to produce electricity. Thus, we created soft, elastic, and transparent artificial leaves consisting of a layer of silicone elastomer on top of an electrode and a flexible element (see Fig. 2a) [2]. The artificial leaves were fixed firmly on the plant leaf at the petiole. In wind, the air flow moves both leaves in a different frequency which creates a recurrent contact and release motion in which the silicone rubber contacts the plant leaf creating triboelectric charges and converting the wind energy into electricity. Again, an electrode in the plant tissue could be used to harvest the charges: one in the plant and one in the artificial leaf to harvest those charges generated on the silicone layer.

This plant-hybrid system was able to directly power LEDs from leaves moving in the wind and a temperature sensor [2]. A further study showed, that the mechanical behavior of the artificial component is crucial and may vary from plant leaf to plant leaf [3]. Thus, to further increase power outputs (usually typically in the range of $15 \mu W/cm^2$ contact area at 1N impact force and 10 Hz stimulus frequency), it is necessary to engineer the mechanical behavior of the artificial leaf, to increase impact force and contact area while not harming the natural leaf. Yet, in none of our studies, mostly done with *Rhododendron* and *Nerium oleander*, we found damage on the leaves or branches. Hence, it was possible to convert wind energy into electricity by plants modified with simple silicone-based artificial leaves.

Since the energy conversion is proportional to the wind speed, the artificial leaves could be used as self-powered wind sensors: in a recent work, an energy harvester connected to a capacitor and a microcontroller was able to send a notification on social media whenever wind became too strong [4]. Thus

plant-hybrid energy harvesters in the future could monitor weather phenomena at the plant level.

C. Further integration of the biohybrid system

We were curious about how to further reduce the artificial modification of the plant and came up with a solution by directly coating the natural leaf with a thin silicone elastomer layer and exploiting a configuration in which an uncoated leaf touches a coated leaf (Fig. 2b) [5]. In this configuration, installing artificial leaves was not required and replaced by a simple paint or spray coating. The contact between a coated and an uncoated leaf produced a significant voltage of about 20 V amplitude while the contact between two uncoated leaves produced a marginal potential in the mV range. It was also possible to power a temperature sensor with the electricity harvested from these modified plants. Besides, for over year, the coating did not harm the plant and it did not significantly alter photosynthesis and transpiration as coating was applied only on the upper leaf surface [5].

Fig. 2. A) Overview of biohybrid wind energy harvester and structure of the artificial leaf installed on the plant leaf (adapted from [2] and [3]). B) Example of further integration of the artificial leaf by a silicone coating of the plant leaf (adapted from [5]).

D. Multisource energy conversion with the same plant

Exploiting other potential energy sources with the same plant could be an interesting additional feature. We observed during our experiments, that plants can be used as unmatched Marconi-antennas for multi-band radio frequency (RF) energy conversion and that feature is possible in the same configuration as used for wind energy harvesting [5]. To realize this, the plant is connected to a bridge rectifier with an earth connection to create a large potential difference. This could charge a capacitor as function of the RF input and the plant could for example receive radio transmission such as “Radio Cuore” transmitting nearby the experimental site. It was also possible to simultaneously harvest wind and RF energy. Both methods did not interfere with each other, or at least, they still showed a positive power balance reaching over 1000% higher energy output compared to only one energy harvesting methods [5].

E. Electricity from rain drops landing on the plant leaves

Another source of mechanical energy widely available in the environment is the impingement of rain drops on plant leaves. Leaves form one of the largest biointerfaces on earth and the contact with water droplets with a high kinetic energy is a crucial phenomenon. We recently showed in detail how a single water drop creates an electrical current in the tissue [6].

The currents measured by an electrode inserted in the stem form on the leaf by liquid-solid contact electrification. The associated current amplitude (typically in the nA range) depends strongly on the leaf surface properties. Superhydrophobic leaves that are densely covered with nanostructured wax architectures, resulted in largest electrical potentials generated. The results suggest that these enhanced signals are a result from the waxes’ chemical and structural features and only to some extent due to superhydrophobicity [6]. Further research is required to use the currents generated by droplet-leaf interactions for sensing and energy harvesting. Yet, it clearly shows the multiple opportunities plant leaves provide as a platform for mechanical energy conversion.

Fig. 3. A) Current and voltage due to water droplets landing on superhydrophobic (*C. antiqorum*) and hydrophilic (*A. macrorrhiza*) leaves. B) Effect of wax structure on current in *C. antiqorum*. Adapted from [6].

III. CONCLUSIONS

Progress on plant-hybrid devices for energy conversion show that plants can be exploited for converting different energy sources (here wind, rain, and ambient RF) into electricity which could be used to power commercial electronics like LEDs and sensors. It is also possible to tune artificial components to enhance power outputs and to be integrated in the biological structure in the best possible way. This biohybrid approach may enable to replace some artificial components in high-tech devices that could at some timepoint be mainly based on biological tissue like plants due to their fascinating and special material properties.

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